

Exclusion Method

Before conducting the interviews, we guided potential participants to answer the following questions to determine their involvement in managing their child's digital safety.

For parents, we primarily asked:

- Has your child been diagnosed with intellectual disability?
- How old is your child? What grade are they in?
- What types of mobile devices does your child use daily (e.g., smartphone, tablet, smartwatch)?
- What is the frequency of your child's mobile device usage?
- What activities does your child primarily use these mobile devices for (e.g., entertainment, communication, etc.)?

For teachers, we primarily asked:

- Are you a teacher at a special education school or a rehabilitation institution?
- How many years of experience do you have in this field?
- Does your institution allow students to use personal devices?
- What types of mobile devices do you observe your students using regularly (e.g., smartphone, tablet, smartwatch)?
- What activities do you observe your students primarily using these mobile devices for (e.g., entertainment, communication, learning, etc.)?

These questions helped us exclude parents and teachers who belong to special education but are not involved in the digital safety practices of children.